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**International Journal on Cybernetics &
Informatics (IJCI)**

ISSN : 2277 - 548X (Online) ; 2320 - 8430 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/index.html>

Data Mining Classification Algorithms for Kidney Disease Prediction

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ABSTRACT

Data mining is a non-trivial process of categorizing valid, novel, potentially useful and ultimately understandable patterns in data. In terms, it accurately state as the extraction of information from a huge database. Data mining is a vital role in several applications such as business organizations, educational institutions, government sectors, health care industry, scientific and engineering. . In the health care industry, the data mining is predominantly used for disease prediction. Enormous data mining techniques are existing for predicting diseases namely classification, clustering, association rules, summarizations, regression and etc. The main objective of this research work is to predict kidney diseases using classification algorithms such as Naïve Bayes and Support Vector Machine. This research work mainly focused on finding the best classification algorithm based on the classification accuracy and execution time performance factors. From the experimental results it is observed that the performance of the SVM is better than the Naive Bayes classifier algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Data mining, Disease prediction, SVM, Naïve Bayes, Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR)

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/papers/4415ijci02.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/Current2015.html>

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Design of a Linear and Wide Range Current Starved Voltage Controlled Oscillator for PLL

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on design and analysis of Current Starved Ring Voltage Controlled Oscillators (CSVCO) for PLL application. The CSVCO circuit is designed and simulated using GPDK 180nm CMOS Technology. The CSVCO has frequency range from 53 MHz to 2.348 GHz and power consumption is 848 μ W. The jitter is improved by connecting a D Flip Flop. In this design the maximum time jitter after D flip flop is 3.1ps and 1.5ps for rising and falling edge respectively and output frequency is from 173MHz to 1.2GHz. The supply voltage VDD is 1.8V.

KEYWORDS

Ring Oscillator, Voltage Controlled Oscillator (VCO), Current Starved Voltage Controlled Oscillator (CSVCO).

For More Details : <http://aircse.org/journal/ijci/papers/2113ijci04.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://aircse.org/journal/ijci/Current2013.html>

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Classification of Diabetes Retina Images Using Blood Vessel Area

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ABSTRACT

Retina images are obtained from the fundus camera and graded by skilled professionals. However there is considerable shortage of expert observers has encouraged computer assisted monitoring. Evaluation of blood vessels network plays an important task in a variety of medical diagnosis. Manifestations of numerous vascular disorders, such as diabetic retinopathy, depend on detection of the blood vessels network. In this work the fundus RGB image is used for obtaining the traces of blood vessels and areas of blood vessels are used for detection of Diabetic Retinopathy (DR). The algorithm developed uses morphological operation to extract blood vessels. Mainly two steps are used: firstly enhancement operation is applied to original retina image to remove noise and increase contrast of retinal blood vessels. Secondly morphology operations are used to take out blood vessels. Experiments are conducted on publicly available DIARETDB1 database. Experimental results obtained by using gray-scale images have been presented.

KEYWORDS

Blood Vessels, Fundus Images, Morphological operations.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/papers/4215ijci24.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/Current2015.html>

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Vehicle License Plate Recognition Using Morphology and Neural Network

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ABSTRACT

Automatic Identification of vehicles is a very challenging area, which is in contrast to the traditional practice of monitoring the vehicles manually. Automatic license plate (LP) recognition is one of the most promising aspects of applying computer vision techniques towards intelligent transportation system. In Location of the vehicle plate, a method of vehicle license plate character segmentation and extraction based on improved edge detection and Mathematical morphology was presented. In the first place, color images were changed into grey images, secondly through calculates the difference of each pixel and neighbourhood pixels to build up images edge and it can make the license plate stand out; Sobel operator is used to extract the edge of objects in image; then the algorithm applies the dilation and erosion mathematical morphology of binary images to get the image smooth contour. The segmentation result which is sent forward to LP recognition stage will improve further processing's efficiency. Neural Network is used to recognize the license plate character. Because of the accuracy of the plate region extraction, the character can be extracted exactly from the plate region .

KEYWORDS

License Plate Recognition, Back propagation, Neural Network, Median Filter

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/papers/2113ijci01.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/Current2013.html>

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A Survey on Privacy Preserving Data Publishing

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ABSTRACT

Data mining is a computational process of analysing and extracting the data from large useful datasets. In recent years, exchanging and publishing data has been common for their wealth of opportunities. Security, Privacy and data integrity are considered as challenging problems in data mining. Privacy is necessary to protect people's interest in competitive situations. Privacy is an ability to create and maintain different sort of social relationships with people. Privacy Preservation is one of the most important factor for an individual since he should not embarrassed by an adversary. The Privacy Preservation is an important aspect of data mining to ensure the privacy by various methods. Privacy Preservation is necessary to protect sensitive information associated with individual. This paper provides a survey of key to success and an approach where individual's privacy would to be non-distracted.

KEYWORDS

Data mining, Privacy, Privacy Preserving

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/papers/3114ijci01.pdf>

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A FUZZY APPROACH FOR SOFTWARE EFFORT ESTIMATION

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ABSTRACT

The most significant activity in software project management is Software development effort prediction. Ubiquitous availability of COCOMO model revealed many possibilities with a perspective of optimization of cost. Cost drivers have significant influence on the COCOMO and this research investigates the role of cost drivers in improving the precision of effort estimation Fuzzy logic has been applied to the COCOMO using membership functions to represent the cost drivers. Using Trapezoidal Membership Function (TMF), a few attributes are assigned the maximum degree of compatibility when they should be assigned lower degrees. To overcome the above limitation, in this paper, it is proposed to use Gaussian Membership Function (GMF) for the cost drivers by studying the behavior of COCOMO cost drivers. It has been found that Gaussian function is performing better than the trapezoidal function, as it demonstrates a smoother transition in its intervals, and the achieved results were closer to the actual effort.

KEYWORDS

COCOMO, Fuzzy based effort estimation, Gaussian membership function, Software cost estimation, Software effort estimation and Project management.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/papers/2113ijci02.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijci/Current2013.html>

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